

Foundation-Model-Driven Parkinson's Disease Auto Diagnosis Challenge: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Foundation-Model-Driven Parkinson's Disease Auto Diagnosis Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

PDCADxFoundation

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The automatic diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD) has received significant attention in recent years due to the high prevalence of PD and the need to improve the accuracy of diagnosis. Clinical diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD) often leverages diagnostic biomarkers in advanced magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Quantitative alterations of tissue property in the deep gray matter (DGM) in MRI may indicate pathophysiological changes related to PD. However, automatic and accurate DGM segmentation faces many challenges, and core brain structures (i.e., SNpr and SNpe) for PD determination are particularly difficult to delineate. The lack of public datasets and quality annotations for PD research has been the bottleneck for developing deep learning models of clinical significance. The Ruijin Imaging Neuroscience Group has curated a multi-parametric MRI dataset for PD research with comprehensive annotations. In this challenge, we will provide a large dataset containing 500 subjects with 3 MR modalities (T1WI, QSM, NM-MRI) and bilateral DGM (CN, PUT, GP, STN, SN, RN, and DN) mask annotations. The challenge participants will compete in the DGM segmentation and PD diagnosis tasks. Publicly accessible foundation models and domain adaptation techniques should be utilized to tackle the challenging PD diagnosis tasks while facing limitations in data scale and annotation. Specifically, two competition tracks are designed: (1) maximize the accuracy of the DGM segmentation using released data and public foundation models (2) maximize the accuracy of PD classification using released data and public foundation models.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Parkinson's disease, Foundation model, Medical image segmentation, Domain Adaptation, Transfer learning

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge learns and extends from the previous competition we hosted at NeurIPS 2023 by pursuing a more detailed technical perspective of foundation model and transfer learning (i.e., model adaptation effectiveness with various data amounts) with a completely new and important clinical application setting (i.e., more clinic-focused tasks). It aims to investigate further how to utilize the power of foundation models to ease the effort of obtaining quality annotations and improve downstream clinical application accuracy. It aligns with the recent trend and success of building foundation models for various downstream applications. The proposed model adaptation paradigm differs from the standard few-shot learning from a methodology perspective.

While it is true that the adaptation of foundation models could require a similar amount of data as conventional fine-tuning/few-shot methods, the fundamental technical routine is different. Our challenge focuses more on evaluating the effectiveness of these domain-adaptation approaches in the context of PD diagnosis. Quality data is often scarce in such specific domains, and developing high-quality models with limited sample cases is crucial for accurate diagnosis, which indeed is clinically more relevant and meaningful.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by neuromelanin (NM) loss in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and iron deposition increase in the substantia nigra (SN) (Nimmri2022he, berg2018movement). Degeneration of the SN becomes obvious when it reaches a 50% to 70% loss of pigmented neurons in the ventral lateral tier of the SNpc. Iron deposition and volume changes of the other deep gray matter (DGM), including the red nucleus (RN), dentate nucleus (DN), and subthalamic nucleus (STN), are also associated with disease progression. Further, the STN serves as an important target for deep brain stimulation treatment in advanced PD patients. Therefore, an accurate in-vivo delineation of the SN and other DGM could be essential for a better PD study.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

50

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We will summarize the challenge results and submit a paper to IEEE TMI or Medical Image Analysis.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

We do not hold any online challenge. The participants will train and test using their own computing resources, and submit the codes, testing results, and technical reports.

TASK 1: PD-related anatomy segmentation and disease classification

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The diagnosis of PD requires special brain imaging modalities and correspondingly trained medical staff. There are 7 anatomical structures related to PD diagnosis, and neurologists use special MRI scanings to localize the anatomies and characterize the disease progression. Despite the high cost and limited availability, the human judgment still suffers from inconsistency. Computed aided diagnosis has been proven successful in many medical image analysis tasks, thus holds huge potential in promoting PD diagnosis. After localizing the related regions, deep learning models can recognize the visual patterns and classify the patient into PD or normal with multi-parametric MRIs. The participants are allowed to use the provided training and validation data (labels for the validation set will only be released together with the testing image data) to develop deep-learning models for structural segmentation and disease classification. Model performance on the test set would be used as the ranking basis (averaged over all structures). The participants are encouraged to utilize foundation models (limited to publicly accessible ones) and transfer learning techniques.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Parkinson's disease, anatomy segmentation, disease classification

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Fakai Wang, Ruijing Hospital, Shanghai Jiaotong University School of Medicine.

Bin Xiao, Ruijing Hospital, Shanghai Jiaotong University School of Medicine.

Mianxin Liu, Shanghai AI Lab.

Zhijia Jin, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Yu Liu, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Yan Li, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Youmin Zhang, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Xiaosong Wang, Shanghai AI Lab.

Naying He, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Fuhua Yan, Radiology Department of Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Fakai Wang (fakaiwang@sjtu.edu.cn), Bin Xiao (xb12501@rjh.com.cn)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

N/A

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://ruijin-imit.github.io/challenges/PDCADxFoundation-MICCAI2025>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Monetary awards for top-3 winners for both tracks.

The winners will be invited to submit their groundbreaking solutions (as coauthors) in a summarization paper. Student participants in the winning teams will be considered for admission and scholarship in organizers' institutes.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.

- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods in the DGM segmentation track will be announced publicly, and top 3 performing methods in the PD classification track will be announced publicly. The organizers will announce the winners of the competition based on the evaluation results, both on the competition website and in the conjunct workshop.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

All members of the participating team qualify as authors

The participating teams may publish their own results separately

No embargo time is defined

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm output should be sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions will be on the organizer's website.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Using the dataset (200 cases in total of the training data), participants will develop model adaptation approaches using foundation models for the PD tasks. The participants should submit model predictions on the validation set several times before submitting the final results of testing predictions. At most 2 submissions of prediction results on the testing set are allowed. See detailed rules on the organizer's website.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

- [Apr. 1, 2025] Website opens for registration
- [Apr. 1, 2025] Release training images & ground truth
- [May 1, 2025] Release validation images
- [May 1, 2025] Submission system opens for validation
- [June 15, 2025] Release validation ground truth
- [June 15, 2025] Release testing images
- [June 15, 2025] Submission system opens for testing
- [Aug. 15, 2025] Testing submission deadline (codes, results, technical reports)
- [Sep. 1, 2025] Release final results of tasks
- [Sep. 10, 2025] Challenge paper submission deadline
- [Sep. 27, 2025] Top-ranking teams report during the MICCAI annual meeting

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

This study was approved by the institutional ethics committee in Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine (No.RJ2022-279). All participants provided written informed consent.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

<https://ruijin-imit.github.io/challenges/PDCADxFoundation-MICCAI2025>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants could submit their results of the validation set (100 cases of the validation data with labels held hidden before the final evaluation phase) to the server during the validation phase (3-5 submissions are allowed). Once the validation phase ends, the organizers will release the labels for the validation set.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

No conflicts of interest for this challenge. Once the validation phase ends, the organizers will release the labels for the validation set.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE**Field(s) of application**

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The data comes from the RING PD project, Ruijin Hospital. There are 500 multi-parametric MRIs (Parkinson's Disease-related modalities: QSM, T1WI, Neuromelanin) obtained in the last few years, with segmentation masks of key regions and PD labels. The derived models will be used in research and diagnosis assistance for PD diagnosis.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The data comes from the RING PD project, Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The in-house RING PD dataset mainly contains three different sequences of MRI image data, i.e., T1 weighted images (T1WI), quantitative susceptibility mapping (QSM), and Neuromelanin MRI (NM-MRI).

MR imaging was carried out on a 3T Ingenia scanner (Philips Healthcare, The Netherlands) using a 15-channel head array coil. T1WI, QSM, and NM-MRI were derived from a single MTC-Strategically Acquired Gradient Echo (STAGE) image (Chen et al., 2018). The imaging parameters were as follows: echo times (TEs) = 7.5 and 17.5 ms, repetition time = 25 ms, flip angles (FA) = 6° and 24°, in-plane resolution = 0.67 mm \times 1.34 mm (interpolated to 0.67 mm \times 0.67 mm), pixel bandwidth = 220 Hz/pixel, imaging matrix size = 384x384, slice thickness = 2 mm (64 slices) and scan time = 1 min 53 s for each FA. For the NM-MRI approach, an activated magnetization transfer contrast (MTC) pulse was used. The MT on-resonance radio-frequency pulse used a nominal flip angle of 90°, zero frequency offset, and a set of three-block pulses with a duration of 1.914 ms. The minimum TR was 62 ms, and seven echoes were collected.

QSM reconstruction and DGM masks: The QSM data were created using the second echo (TE = 17.5 ms) of the STAGE data since a longer TE has a better signal-to-noise ratio in mapping the iron content. The QSM processing steps are (1) Brain extraction (BET) using the BET tool on the first echo magnitude images with a threshold of 0.2, an erosion factor of 2, and an island factor of 2000 (Smith, 2002); (2) using 3DSRNCP (3D sorting following a noncontinuous path) to unwrap the phase (Abdul-Rahman et al., 2007); (3) using SHARP (sophisticated harmonic artifact reduction processing) to remove background phase (Schweser et al., 2011); and (4) conducting four iterations and a threshold of 0.1 to reconstruct the susceptibility maps (Haacke et al., 2010; Tang et al., 2013).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Annotation for the deep brain nuclei structures: One neuroradiologist manually segmented the CN, GP, PUT, SN, RN, and DN in the bilateral hemisphere. Another radiologist with 5 years of experience in neuroimaging double-checked all the structural boundaries. Finally, those ROIs approved by these two radiologists will serve as the ground truth for the segmentation model.

Annotation for the SN, STN structures: The ROIs for the NM-rich region (SNpc, SN) were manually traced by a single rater on MTC magnitude images and QSM maps using SPIN software (SpinTech, Inc., Bingham Farms, MI). The NM-based SN boundaries were traced from the last caudal slice for three to five slices until the NM-rich region was no longer visible. Simultaneously, the iron-based SN boundaries were traced starting from one slice below the most cranial slice where the STN was visible and continued for four to six consecutive slices to the most caudal slice. The STN ROIs were traced from the top of the RN for two slices cranially. For all the ROIs, a dynamic programming approach (DPA) was used to determine the final boundaries to alleviate the subjective bias. All these boundaries were then reviewed by a second rater and modified accordingly in consensus with the first rater.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The diagnosis of PD was based on the MDS PD criteria. The inclusion criteria for the Healthy Control cases were as follows: (1) 35 years or older; (2) no family history of movement disorders; (3) no neurological or psychiatric disorders; and (4) an MMSE score of at least 24.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Multimodal brain MRI images from RING PD dataset, Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Parkinson's disease related anatomy regions shown in multimodal brain MRI images, Parkinson's disease patients

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity,Consistency,Precision

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

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b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

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c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Ruijin Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

None

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Sample image and annotation masks for DGM segmentation. The spatial variations of DGM structures are shown in different slices of the T1WI MRI and QSM MRI respectively. The enlarged 3D mask on the top right corner demonstrates the volume differences among DGM structures. Each DGM structure has the left and right regions, colored separately.

Sample image and annotation masks for SNpc segmentation. The substantia nigra structure is partially seen in QSM MRI, partially seen in NM MRI, and the intersection area is the SNpc region.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The Ruijin-PD dataset includes 500 multi-parametric MRI cases (50% each for PD positives and healthy controls) with more than 105,000 images in total. Each case contains the T1WI, QSM, and NM-MRI images, with segmentation masks on 7 PD-related anatomical structures. The PD classification label is also included. The images for training (200 cases, with labels) and validation (100 cases, without labels) will be freely available at the competition start date, while the testing images (200 cases) will be available at the test stage (together with the labels for the validation set). The label for the test set will not be released. All the data and ground truth have not been previously published and have been kept confidential.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The data splitting is based on the cross-validation principle, for maximum randomness and reliability. The split proportion ensures adequate training samples and meaningful testing scores.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

None.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Annotation for the deep brain nuclei structures: One neuroradiologist manually segmented the CN, GP, PUT, SN, RN, and DN in the bilateral hemisphere. Another radiologist with 5 years of experience in neuroimaging double-checked all the structural boundaries. Finally, those ROIs approved by these two radiologists will serve as the ground truth for the segmentation model.

Annotation for the SN, STN structures: The ROIs for the NM-rich region (SNpc, SN) were manually traced by a single rater on MTC magnitude images and QSM maps using SPIN software (SpinTech, Inc., Bingham Farms, MI). The NM-based SN boundaries were traced from the last caudal slice for three to five slices until the NM-rich region was no longer visible. Simultaneously, the iron-based SN boundaries were traced starting from one slice below the most cranial slice where the STN was visible and continued for four to six consecutive slices to the most caudal slice. The STN ROIs were traced from the top of the RN for two slices cranially. For all the ROIs, a dynamic programming approach (DPA) was used to determine the final boundaries to alleviate the subjective bias. All these boundaries were then reviewed by a second rater and modified accordingly in consensus with the first rater.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

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c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The diagnosis of PD was based on the MDS PD criteria. The inclusion criteria for the Healthy Control cases were as follows: (1) 35 years or older; (2) no family history of movement disorders; (3) no neurological or psychiatric disorders; and (4) an MMSE score of at least 24.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

inter- and intra-annotator variability

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

To evaluate the model performance for procedures involved in the PD diagnosis, we adopt segmentation metrics and classification metrics for corresponding models. The segmentation metrics include the Dice Coefficient and the Hausdorff Distance 95% percentile (HD95). For each segmentation region, the algorithms have separate Dice ranking and HD95 ranking. If the prediction of a region is missing, then it would rank at the bottom. The final ranking score is the average of all these rankings normalized by the number of teams. Therefore the final ranking status depends on the overall segmentation performance of all regions. It is noted that images with bad quality are excluded from the evaluation of segmentation performance. We will provide the codes and instructions for evaluation upon the data release.

For the PD classification task, we adopt the accuracy (Acc) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC). Accuracy reflects the overall correct predictions among all the test images. The predicted label is determined with the maximum softmax outputs in the multi-class classification task. AUROC is computed for the PD class to measure the capability of distinguishing between positive and negative classes at various threshold settings. The Acc and AUROC would have separate rankings, the final PD ranking will be determined by the average ranking of Acc and AUROC.

For each submission, missing results of testing cases are not allowed in general when the results for all testing cases will be automatically computed. If the submitted solution fails to generate the results for certain cases, a default output of 'no finding' (indicating an empty mask or non-PD) will be used to compute the evaluation metrics. For the cases without valid output, we set the ranks for the corresponding metrics to the maximum.

To assess whether the performance difference is significant, we will use paired and unpaired rank-based and t-test statistics for errors compared with permutation-generated one-sided null distributions.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

To evaluate the model performance for procedures involved in the PD diagnosis, we adopt segmentation metrics and classification metrics for corresponding models. The segmentation metrics include the Dice Coefficient and the Hausdorff Distance 95% percentile (HD95).

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Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

For the DGM segmentation task, we adopt the Dice and HD95 as metrics. For each segmentation region, the algorithms have separate Dice ranking and HD95 ranking. If the prediction of a region is missing, then it would rank at the bottom. The final ranking score is the average of all these rankings normalized by the number of teams. Therefore the final ranking status depends on the overall segmentation performance of all regions. It is noted that images with bad quality are excluded from the evaluation of segmentation performance. We will provide the codes and instructions for evaluation upon the data release.

For the PD classification task, we adopt the Acc and AUROC as metrics. The Acc and AUROC would have separate rankings, the final PD ranking will be determined by the average ranking of Acc and AUROC normalized by the number of teams.

For each submission, missing results of testing cases are not allowed in general when the results for all testing cases will be automatically computed. If the submitted solution fails to generate the results for certain cases, a

default output of 'no finding' (indicating an empty mask or non-PD) will be used to compute the evaluation metrics. For the cases without valid output, we set the ranks for the corresponding metrics to the maximum.

To assess whether the performance difference is significant, we will use paired and unpaired rank-based and t-test statistics for errors compared with permutation-generated one-sided null distributions.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For each submission, missing results of testing cases are not allowed in general when the results for all testing cases will be automatically computed. If the submitted solution fails to generate the results for certain cases, a default output of 'no finding' (indicating an empty mask or non-PD) will be used to compute the evaluation metrics. For the cases without valid output, we set the ranks for the corresponding metrics to the maximum.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For the DGM segmentation task, we adopt the Dice and HD95 as metrics. For each segmentation region, the algorithms have separate Dice ranking and HD95 ranking. If the prediction of a region is missing, then it would rank at the bottom. The final ranking score is the average of all these rankings normalized by the number of teams. Therefore the final ranking status depends on the overall segmentation performance of all regions. It is noted that images with bad quality are excluded from the evaluation of segmentation performance. We will provide the codes and instructions for evaluation upon the data release.

For the PD classification task, we adopt the Acc and AUROC as metrics. The Acc and AUROC would have separate rankings, the final PD ranking will be determined by the average ranking of Acc and AUROC normalized by the number of teams.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

For each submission, missing results of testing cases are not allowed in general when the results for all testing cases will be automatically computed. If the submitted solution fails to generate the results for certain cases, a default output of 'no finding' (indicating an empty mask or non-PD) will be used to compute the evaluation metrics. For the cases without valid output, we set the ranks for the corresponding metrics to the maximum.

To assess whether the performance difference is significant, we will use paired and unpaired rank-based and t-test statistics for errors compared with permutation-generated one-sided null distributions.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

N/A

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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keywords = {Foundation models},
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abstract = {Abstract Parkinson's disease (PD) diagnosis based on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is still challenging clinically. Quantitative susceptibility maps (QSM) can potentially provide underlying pathophysiological information by detecting the iron distribution in deep gray matter (DGM) nuclei. We hypothesized that deep learning (DL) could be used to automatically segment all DGM nuclei and use relevant features for a better differentiation between PD and healthy controls (HC). In this study, we proposed a DL-based
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pipeline for automatic PD diagnosis based on QSM and T1-weighted (T1W) images. This consists of (1) a convolutional neural network model integrated with multiple attention mechanisms which simultaneously segments caudate nucleus, globus pallidus, putamen, red nucleus, and substantia nigra from QSM and T1W images, and (2) an SE-ResNeXt50 model with an anatomical attention mechanism, which uses QSM data and the segmented nuclei to distinguish PD from HC. The mean dice values for segmentation of the five DGM nuclei are all >0.83 in the internal testing cohort, suggesting that the model could segment brain nuclei accurately. The proposed PD diagnosis model achieved area under the the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUCs) of 0.901 and 0.845 on independent internal and external testing cohorts, respectively. Gradient-weighted class activation mapping (Grad-CAM) heatmaps were used to identify contributing nuclei for PD diagnosis on patient level. In conclusion, the proposed approach can potentially be used as an automatic, explainable pipeline for PD diagnosis in a clinical setting.},

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A